

I.H. 1.63

Vert. $\angle$ 100.3^R

~~90.2~~^o .30^R

.27^o

cos 999988896

slope dis: 50.711

P = 50.71

100.3075

.3075^R

~~27656~~^o

.27675^o

.663^R

.5967^o

.660

.594

4.0193

3.61737

29.23763202

104.2548

3.82914

33.063

$\angle$ 107.7452

7.7452^R

.67068^o

7.6741^R

6.90669

17.476

104.2856^R

3.85704^o

35.68299439

245

3.32

19.25

2.505

I.H. 21.755

→ 1.555

→ 3.05

I.H. 23.25

→ .27 (B)

→ 2.515

{ This I.H. cutting is
25 cm above top back
Sphinx

25.495 I.H.

→ .485 Transfer pt. C

→ 3.745

I.H. 28.755

→ .56 Trans. pt. D

→ 3.275

I.H. 31.47 - passes 30-50 cm
above Sphinx head top

→ .24 Trans. pt. E = Geo pt. 24 top

→ 3.72

I.H. 34.95

Geo pt. 22 18.475

Transfer pt. A 20.2

→ 1295 G.P. 23
= 21.955

Transfer pt. B 22.98

→ 1.93 bottom thin marly units at base

Geo. pt. 24 = 23.565

Trans. pt. C = 25.01

Trans. pt. D 28.195

→ .24 Geo pt. 24 top
= 31.23

→ 31.23

→ Geo pt. 21 → .675 34.275

I.H. 23.34 - is 20-30 cm above top
back Sphinx behind head
→ 3.12 on A (20.22 - 2 cm off)
(accepted - O.K.)

→ 1.625 on A 20.22 - O.K.

I.H. 21.545

→ Geo pt. 22 3.35 = 18.495

↳ 2 cm error

→ 490/3038.04 2.575

19.27

CLOSED to within
2 cm.

BACK CHECK I.H. 34.95

→ 3.72

Geo pt. 24 =
Trans. pt. E

→ .865

E ok - O.K.

I.H. 32.095

→ 3.895 on D

→ .46

I.H. 28.60 gives 28.2 on D
D - O.K.

→ 3.645 on C; C - O.K.

→ 0.325 on C; C - O.K.

I.H. 25.34

→ 2.35 on B; (22.99) O.K.

→ .35 on B; 22.99 - O.K.

I.H. 23.34

Geo Point 25 - Elevation run

B.M. 8 Nail in Brick in ^{Modern} AII Temple MSL GS

SW corner
E500-N.2963.79 25.306
~~25.~~ 15.975

15.975
→ 2.85

I.H. 18.825
→ 0.10 18.725 T.P. A
→ 3.41

I.H. 22.135
→ .545 21.59 T.P. B
→ 3.715

I.H. 25.305
→ .35 24.955 T.P. C
→ 2.39

I.H. 27.345
→ 2.90 24.445 - Geo pt. 25

CHECK BACK

I.H. ~~25.305~~ 27.345
→ 2.39 T.P. C O.K.
→ .20

I.H. 25.155
→ 3.555 T.P. B 21.60 O.K.
→ .69

I.H. 22.29 21.60 O.K.
→ ~~3.01~~ T.P. A
→ 3.405

2.865

MSL GS

500-3027 22.916 13.585

→ 3.64⁵ I.H. 17.23

→ .21 → .21 Tran pt. A 17.02

→ 2.29

I.H. 19.31

→ .08⁵ on 490/3038.04

19.22⁵

256.663
256.651
256.656
256.661
256.660

I.H. 1.62

STATION E490-N3038.04 Top NW corner V.T.

0° → Canyon Axis to E600, E602

Geo point 22

Horizontal $\angle$ 338.2716^R

Vertical $\angle$ 100.3606^R

.3606^R

.32454°

Slope distance 142.188 m

D = 142.185719 m

Geo Point 23

Horizontal $\angle$ 345.624^R

Vertical $\angle$ 99.1146^R Tran 100

.8854^R

.79686°

Slope D 192.316 ~~142.188~~

D = 192.2974007

Geo point 24

Horizontal $\angle$ 350.9539

Vertical $\angle$ 97.0385^R

2.9615^R

2.66535

Average Slope D 256.66582

D = 256.3881538

Geo Point 25

Horizontal Angle 100.0969^R

Vertical " 90.609^R

9.391^R

8.4519°

Slope D 94.502 94.502 94.501

D = 93.47567061 m

(Residue II)
Member I-II Contact top of Amphitheater
N. Ledge